

**Locus of Control as Correlate of Lecturers' use of Multimedia Technologies in Colleges
of Education in Southwest, Nigeria**

ADESANYA Olusegun Oyeleye Ph.D

College Library

Michael Otedola College of Primary Education

Noforija- Epe, Lagos State

sanyaseg22@gmail.com

Submitted: December 3, 2018.

Locus of Control as Correlate of Lecturers' Use of Multimedia Technologies in Colleges of Education in Southwest, Nigeria

Abstract

The study investigated locus of control as a correlate of lecturers' multimedia technologies utilisation in Colleges of Education in Southwest, Nigeria. This is for the purpose of ascertaining the relationship between lecturers' locus of control and their multimedia technologies utilisation in colleges of education in southwest, Nigeria. The descriptive research design was adopted, while a multi-stage sampling procedure was used in the study. Stratified sampling technique was used to select colleges of education and simple random sampling method was employed to select lecturers from the selected colleges of education. A total of 862 lecturers (627 males and 235 females) participated in the study. A structured questionnaire tagged "Lecturers' Questionnaire on locus of control and Multimedia Technologies Utilisation in Colleges of Education in south west Nigeria" (LQLOCMTUCUESWN) with the reliability coefficient of 0.80 was used for data collected. Three research questions were answered in the course of the study. The result showed that inter locus of control of lecturers was low while their external locus of control was high, lecturers multimedia technologies utilisation in colleges of education in southwest Nigeria is at average level. The finding also revealed a significant relationship between lecturers locus of control and their multimedia technologies utilisation in colleges of education in south west Nigeria. Therefore locus of control could be considered as correlate of lecturers' use of multimedia technologies in Colleges of Education in south west, Nigeria.

Keywords: locus of control, multimedia technologies utilisation and colleges of education.

Introduction

Multimedia technologies are perceived as vehicle for an enhanced curriculum delivery and implementation by academic staff in the tertiary institutions globally, these technologies are audio, visual and audio-visual resources which could be employed in the classroom for the purpose of promoting teaching and learning processes to improving students learning outcomes. Multimedia technologies also include print, non-print and electronic media like television, radio, video disc player, projectors of different kinds, internet resources among others. Multimedia technologies are information carriers that can be used to facilitate instructional delivery because, they are essential for sharing educational information between instructors and learners in the institutions of learning all over the world. Consequently, it is assumed that lecturers around the world are doing everything possible to make sure multimedia technologies are core part of teaching and learning facilities provided for. Tertiary institutions are becoming more engaged in efforts to improve the use of multimedia technologies in enhancing teaching and learning processes.

Pointing out the role of multimedia technologies in instructional delivery process in Colleges of Education, from observation the role of multimedia technologies in education while the use of multimedia technologies are rapidly becoming one of the most widely discussed educational issues in literature, such that careful selection and organisation of subject content to be taught, as well as the ability to deliver a clear and well-organised instruction especially to learners of varying learning abilities must be considered in the choose of media resources to be used. Specifically, multimedia technologies utilisation make teaching/ learning arrangement enjoyable and motivating with changing images, sounds, symbols, its effects could also be helpful in teaching concepts, ideas and reduce boredom on the part of the teachers and learners. Multimedia resources provide the teachers with vast qualities of information in an easily accessible, sequential or non-sequential format which can be used as teaching tools in Colleges of Education (Onasanya, 2004, Aleburu 2008 and Taiwo, 2008).

Multimedia technologies are potential tools for knowledge presentations, which offer exceptional advantages in educational fields. According to Hoffman (2002) text alone cannot give students a reality experience of any literature play in cultural and creative art, he further stated that in teaching educational courses, instructional aid enhance knowledge transfer in classroom. Multimedia technologies provide opportunity for instructors to make available various ways the students can have realistic experience of their subject in diverse manner. Multimedia technologies present knowledge using synchronized still images, audio, motion pictures and animation in a sequential manner. Multimedia technologies enable a learning environment that is self-paced, learner-controlled and individualised learning. Egunjobi (2012) pointed out that educational media contain materials that have educational content which can enhance teachers' achievement and learning objectives when used in institutions of learning at any educational level.

Multimedia technologies utilisation can be shaped or influenced by certain psychological factors, specifically locus of control; this is classified into internal and external locus of control. Locus of control could enhance multimedia technologies utilisation in colleges of education. This factor shape both lecturers and students scholarly and academic abilities, curriculum development and the overall processes in schooling (Mccoach, Gable and Madara, 2013). Locus of control is a psychological, social learning theory that refers to the extent to which individuals perceive control over their lives, and environment (Lefcourt, 1982 cited by Akinjide, 2010).

Locus of control as a concept was originally developed by Rotter in the 1950s, and identified two types of locus of control, the internal and external locus of control. This concept shows how individuals' decision making ability is influenced. From Rotter's theory of social learning, locus of control has relevance with multimedia technologies utilisation. According to Rotter, locus of control is a personality variable which refers to individual's perception of the main causes of events in life.

Locus of control is an individual's beliefs about the controls the outcomes in his life, the internal locus of control are individuals who believes their action in life determined their outcome, while the external locus of control believe that their outcome are controlled by factors such as luck and other people. Locus of control is an important variable for the explanation of human behaviour in organisations. It is a personality trait measured in terms of an internal or external focus. It is one factor that may affect the decision-making process which includes multimedia technologies utilisation (Akintayo, 2016).

Individuals with internal locus of control always trust that their action has effect on their come in life and their achievement capacity, these people are called internals. They have a tendency to be self-assured. They control their very own future and consider themselves to be successful specialists in deciding the event of strengthening occasions throughout everyday life. External locus of control is the opposite of the internal locus of control as people in this gathering trust that natural powers decide their life and occasions around, they accuse the environment and could be irresponsible, agreeable or forceful and feel unreliable of results of occasion and result of their own actions. Such individual is seen as 'externals' (Chung and Ding, 2002) they also express that researchers who have faith in outside control of fortresses credit their outcomes to the fate, good fortune, destiny influence of others et cetera, these researchers are called facades.

Kay-cheng, (2015) in an investigation on Locus of control as an arbitrator of teachers stress, managed an educator locus of control scale to 74 lecturers at a technical school and 40 teachers from a secondary school. The consequence of the correlations demonstrated no significant contrasts in both internality-externality and stress in general between the 2 tests. It is presumed that outcomes bolster, in the educational context, the recommendation that locus of control works as an arbitrator of stress. The implication of this is people with internal locus of control may likely certainly change their conduct following reinforcements than those people with external locus of control.

Konan (2013) investigated the view of supervisors' and student locus of control and internet use, he hypothesis locus of control and internet use among students and expressed that internet users are more probable than nonusers to have and internal locus of control because of the high level of controllability inherent in the circumstance of the device. His finding revealed that there are limited researches on the connection between locus of control and the web related programmes utilisation. Adeagbo (2015) referring to Welsh (1999) examined the relationship between internet utilisation, adapting style, experiencing and locus of control among undergraduate in private universities in the northeast Nigeria where internet reliance was characterised as students showing 3 criteria from a rundown of 7 things., the finding of the study revealed there was an inclination that dependent users have a more external locus of control, a discovery which approached significance.

Bothma and Schepers (1997) researched on the role of locus of control and accomplishment motivation on job performance, the finding presumed that Locus of Control Inventory (LCI) is a superior indicator of work execution than accomplishment inspiration, while Van Staden et al. (2000) researched the connection between locus of control and transformational authority. The outcomes showed a high level of locus of control among supervisors and that there is a strong relationship connection between internal locus of control and transformational leadership; external locus of control and value-based authority; and self-rule and transformational leadership. Rothmann and Agathagelou (2000) scanned for a connection between locus of control, work fulfilment and efficiency, they found a positive relationship between locus of control and occupation satisfaction. They found a negative connection between an external locus of control and employment fulfilment.

In a related report which inspected students' locus of control and learning capacity of web based and conventional programmes. Dille and Mezack (1991) reported that students' internal locus of control among web based programme is higher compared to their external locus of control, the study further revealed that there is a relationship between students locus of control and web based or conventional course. They found that students with an internal locus of control are more determined in distance education than those with an external locus of control. Wang and Newlin (2000) found a huge contrast between online students in psychology (the individuals who selected for electronic classes) and conventional students (the individuals who enlisted for face to face classes). Online students showed a more prominent external locus of control than

their partners in customary courses, and there is relationship between locus of control and student performance in web based course or conventional course.

Nevertheless, according to Ishiyama et al. (1999), students' locus of control may influence the assessment and performance, they recommended that students who have an internal locus of control ought to incline toward learning conditions that boost their level of their learning power and that a web-based learning condition might simply be such a situation. The Internet has officially changed the manner in which people work together and the manner in which they learn which will be a continuous process (Chak and Leung, 2004).

Hengstler, (2001) stipulated that locus of control of student will profit better with web-based learning, web based information can help individual learner to improve their learning techniques in upgrading their typical locus of control with a specific end goal to accomplish scholarly profitability and vocation achievement. At the hierarchical level, information of the impact of locus of control on internet learning can encourage instruction, preparing and advancement specialists to outline compelling web based learning programs, (Lau and Shaffer, 1999; Dollinger, 2000).

In view of these, due to the fall in the quality and quantity education and which has lead to increase in failure rate in examinations, poor performance of students in both internally and externally and has demand an improvement in teaching and learning activities. Also some lecturers' scholarly values influenced by psychological factors could improve their job effectiveness at all academic levels in Nigeria. It is against this foregoing, that this study investigated lecturers' locus of control as correlate of multimedia technologies utilisation in colleges of education in Southwest Nigeria.

Objectives of the study

The main objective of this study is to investigate the relationship between lecturers' use of multimedia technologies and their locus of control in colleges of education in southwest, Nigeria. The specific objectives are: To

1. examine lecturers level of locus of control in colleges of education in South-west, Nigeria
2. examine the frequency of multimedia technologies utilisation by lecturers in colleges of education in South-west, Nigeria;

3. find out the relationship between lecturers locus of control and their multimedia technologies utilisation in colleges of education in south-west, Nigeria;
4. find out the relative contribution of lecturers locus of control and their multimedia technologies utilisation in colleges of education in south-west, Nigeria

Research Questions

This study will provide answer to the following research questions:

1. What are the level of lecturers' locus of control in colleges of education in South-west, Nigeria?
2. What is the frequency of multimedia technologies utilisation by lecturers during lectures in colleges of education in South-west, Nigeria?
3. What is the relationship between lecturers' locus of control and multimedia technologies utilisation in colleges of education in South-west, Nigeria?
4. What is the relative contribution of lecturers' locus of control and their multimedia technologies utilisation in colleges of education in south-west, Nigeria?

Methodology

Research Design

The study adopted a descriptive survey design of correlation type. This design was adopted for the study because it is considered the appropriate method in obtaining reliable information about the existing variables investigated in the study, there was no manipulation of any variable.

Population and Sampling Techniques

The total population for this study was based on lecturers in colleges of education in south-western Nigeria. Multi-stage sampling procedure was adopted. Stratified sampling method was used to select colleges of education and simple random sampling method was used to select lecturers for the study. This method was employed for equal representation of respondents from the selected colleges of education in South-western Nigeria. Meanwhile sample of 1098 lecturers were selected for the study.

Instrumentation

The main instrument for data collection is the structured questionnaire tagged Lecturers' Questionnaire on Lecturers' Locus of Control and Multimedia Technologies Utilisation in

Colleges of Education in South Western Nigeria (QLLOCTUCOESWN). The items in the questionnaire were designed by the investigators. The questionnaire was administered to the lecturers from the selected Colleges of Education which consisted of both Federal and state. The items were designed to examine the relationship between lecturers' locus of control and multimedia technologies influence of multimedia technologies on lecturers' research output in colleges of education in south-west, Nigeria. The questionnaire was validated and trial-tested on 20 lecturers apart those used for the study. The reliability coefficient locus of control and multimedia technologies was 0.80 respectively which was found reliable and adequate for the study.

Data Analysis

The data collected were analysed using frequency, percentage, mean, standard deviation and multiple regression.

Response rate

The total of 1096 questionnaires was administered to lecturers, out of which 862 (78.6%) copies were valid and found usable for the study.

Findings

The findings revealed that 627(72.7%) of the respondents were males while 235(27.3%) of them were female. On respondent age 46(5.3%) are less than 30 years of age, 213(24.7%) are aged 31-40 years, 417(48.4%) are aged 41-50 years, 147(17.1%) are aged 51-60 years and 39(4.5%) are aged 61 years and above. Also 121(14.0%) had less than 5 years of experience, 301(34.9%) had 5-10 years of experience, 117(13.6%) had 11-15 years of experience, 169(19.6%) had 16-20 years of experience, 120(13.9%) had 21-25 years of experience, 10(1.2%) had 26-30 years of experience and 24(2.8%) had 31-35 years of experience.

Table 1: level of lecturers' locus of control in colleges of education in South-west, Nigeria

S/N	Statement	Strongly Disagreed (%)	Disagreed (%)	Agreed (%)	Strongly agreed (%)	Mean	S.D
Internal locus of control							
1	My personal interest, skills, abilities, professional exposure and multimedia technologies skills influence me, hence my teaching effectiveness is	5 0.6%	15 1.7%	373 43.3%	469 54.4%	3.51	.57

	greatly enhanced.						
2	Taking an active part in multimedia aided academic work can control events in teaching.	19 2.2%	30 3.5%	524 60.8%	289 33.5%	3.27	.71
4	Multimedia technology skills are determined by my personal agitation and hard work to influence my job productivity.	25 2.9%	77 8.9%	480 55.7%	280 32.5%	3.18	.71
5	There is an immediate association between how I study and effective use of these multimedia technologies to influence my job productivity.	69 8.0%	127 14.7%	495 57.4%	171 19.8%	3.02	.44
6	My trial and error skill and ability influence my multimedia technology skill to influence my job productivity.	19 2.2%	169 19.6%	478 55.5%	196 22.7%	2.99	.72
7	My subject background has little or no influence on my use of multimedia technologies for job productivity.	226 26.2%	267 31.0%	200 23.2%	169 19.6%	2.36	1.0 7
8	No matter how hard I try, I am not influenced to use multimedia technologies to enhance my job productivity.	226 26.2%	404 46.9%	157 18.2%	75 8.7%	2.09	.89
9	It is difficult for me to have much control over the class when using multimedia technologies for academic work	249 28.9%	441 51.2%	132 15.3%	40 40.6%	1.96	.79
10	I feel stressed using multimedia technologies during teaching especially with a small populated class.	324 37.6%	339 39.3%	155 18.0%	44 5.1%	1.90	.87
N=862		Weighted mean 2.43			Criterion mean =		
2.50							
External locus of control							
1	I apply knowledge acquired through discussion with colleagues and group to improve my multimedia technologies ability for academic productivity.	3 0.3%	44 5.1%	557 64.6%	258 29.9%	3.24	.55
2	Multimedia technologies utilisation has influenced my academic productivity greatly through the assistance of Colleagues in my workplace.	27 3.1%	65 7.5%	498 57.8%	272 31.6%	3.18	.70
3	Multimedia technology skill is	45	85	514	218	3.05	.75

	acquired by getting along with the IT experts around me to enhance my job productivity.	5.2%	9.9%	59.6%	25.3%		
4	Workshops and conferences attendance has influenced my use of multimedia technologies while personal exposure has less influence on its use to enhance my job productivity.	43 5.0%	167 19.4%	395 45.8%	257 29.8%	3.00	.83
5	Personal and professional background and heredity play the major role in determining my multimedia technologies interest and enhance job productivity.	51 5.9%	100 11.6%	529 61.4%	182 21.1%	2.98	.75
6	Colleague's interest in multimedia technologies utilisation stimulates my interest in the technologies and this has enhanced my job productivity.	42 4.9%	159 18.4%	493 57.2%	168 19.5%	2.91	.75
7	On the job training goes a long way in influencing my multimedia utilisation technologies for academic effectiveness	87 10.1%	109 12.6%	468 54.3%	198 23.0%	2.90	.87
8	It is work experiences in life which determine multimedia technologies interest and it has contributed significantly to my job productivity.	84 9.7%	183 21.2%	428 49.7%	167 19.4%	2.79	.87
9	The Institution Management where I work does not really encourage the use of multimedia technologies for job productivity.	242 28.1%	304 35.3%	124 14.4%	192 22.3%	2.31	1.1 1
10	Sometime I teach using multimedia technologies but I don't really understand the effect on my job productivity.	228 26.5%	369 42.8%	198 23.0%	67 7.8%	2.12	.89
N = 862		Weighted average=2.85		Criterion mean = 2.50			

Table 1 revealed lecturers' level of control in colleges of education in south-west, Nigeria, this is divided into internal and external. Lecturers' personal interest, skills professional exposure and multimedia technologies utilisation enhance their teaching effectiveness ranked highest by the mean score rating and was followed by Taking an active part in multimedia aided academic work can control events in teaching , (mean =3.27), Multimedia technology skills are determined by my personal agitation and hard work to influence my job

productivity, (mean =3.18). on other side of the continuum, least of the respondent indicated that no matter how hard they try, nothing influence them to use multimedia technologies to enhance my job productivity, (mean =2.09), some have major difficulty in having control over the class when using multimedia technologies for academic work, (mean =1.96) and lastly some lecturers feel stressed using multimedia technologies during teaching especially with a small populated class, (mean =1.90).

Also the finding further revealed that applying knowledge acquired through discussion with colleagues and group to improve lecturers use of multimedia technologies ability for academic productivity, (mean =3.24) is ranked highest on lectures external locus of control, followed by multimedia technologies utilization influencing lecturers academic productivity greatly through the assistance of colleagues in workplace, (mean =3.18),Multimedia technology skill acquired by getting along with the IT experts around them to enhance my job productivity, (mean =3.05). While the least considered were lecturers’ work experiences in life determining their multimedia technologies interest which has contributed significantly to lecturers’ job productivity, (mean =2.79), The institution management not really encourage the use of multimedia technologies for job productivity, (mean =2.31), sometimes teaching using multimedia technologies and not really understanding the effect on my job productivity, (mean =2.12).

This finding further revealed that lecturers’ internal locus of control weighted mean (2.45) is less than the criterion mean (2.50) while lecturers’ external locus of control weighted mean (2.85) is greater than the criterion mean (2.50). This implies lecturers in colleges of education in south-west, Nigeria exhibited higher level of external locus of control than internal locus of control.

Table 2: Frequency of multimedia technologies utilisation by lecturers in colleges of education in South-west, Nigeria

S/N	Items	Very often (%)	Often (%)	Occasionally (%)	Never (%)	Mean	S.D.
1	CD-ROMs	142 25.0%	66 11.6%	36 6.3%	324 57.0%	3.98	1.30
2	Social Media	148 26.1%	107 18.8%	145 25.5%	168 29.6%	3.87	1.17
3	Mobile Phones	161 28.3%	113 19.9%	143 25.2%	151 26.6%	3.00	1.16
4	Computer Aided	48	115	194	211	2.96	1.01

	Instructional Software	8.5%	20.2%	34.2%	37.1%		
5	Digital Video Disc (DVD/VCD)	82 14.4%	82 14.4%	196 34.5%	262 46.1%	2.94	1.00
6	Teaching Courseware	49 8.6%	56 9.9%	229 40.3%	234 41.2%	2.83	1.07
7	Laptop/ I-pad	256 45.1%	132 23.2%	108 19.0%	72 12.7%	2.54	1.3
8	Interactive Radio and Television Instruction	28 4.9%	43 7.6%	130 22.9%	367 64.6%	2.98	.71
9	Multimedia Animations	59 10.4%	74 13.0%	246 43.3%	189 33.3%	2.32	1.03
10	Multi-media Projector	59 10.4%	74 13.0%	246 43.3%	189 33.3%	2.14	1.03
11	Electronic Interactive Board	87 15.3%	54 9.5%	290 51.1%	137 24.1%	2.00	1.01
12	Video Conferencing Tools	80 14.1%	52 9.2%	151 26.6%	285 50.2%	1.42	.99
13	Simulation Programme and Games	93 16.4%	51 9.0%	305 53.7%	119 21.0%	1.41	1.01
14	Internet Facilities	289 50.9%	165 29.0%	60 10.6%	54 9.5%	1.39	.98
15	Scanners	76 13.4%	45 7.9%	115 20.2%	326 57.4%	1.72	.98
N = 862		Weighted average=2.50			Criterion mean = 2.50		

Table 2 revealed the frequency of Multimedia Technologies Utilized by Lecturers for Academic Activities in Colleges of Education South-west, Mobile Phones, (mean = 3.56) was ranked highest by the mean score rating and was followed by Social Media, (mean = 3.30), Internet Facilities, (mean = 3.12), Laptop/ i –pad, (mean = 3.10), CD-Roms, (mean = 2.30), Teaching Courseware, (mean = 2.25), Computer Aided Instructional Software, (mean = 2.25), Scanners, (mean = 2.24), Digital Video Disc (DVD/VCD), (mean = 2.19), Interactive Radio and Television Instruction, (mean = 2.07), Electronic Interactive Board, (mean = 2.04), Multi-media Projector, (mean = 1.94), Simulation Programme and Games, (mean = 1.91), Multimedia Animations, (mean = 1.89) and lastly by Video Conferencing tools, mean = 1.78). This implies that lecturers in colleges of education utilise multimedia technologies although its utilisation is on the average, since the weighted mean (2.50) is equal to the criterion mean (2.50).

Table 3: Relative contribution of Locus of Control on lecturers Multimedia Technologies Utilisation in Colleges of Education in south-west, Nigeria

Model	Unstandardized Coefficient	Stand. Coefficient	T	Sig.
-------	----------------------------	--------------------	---	------

	B	Std. Error	Beta Contribution		
(Constant)	28.611	2.138		13.380	.000
Locus of Control	.221	.028	.260	7.973	.000
Multimedia Technologies Utilization	.112	.022	.163	5.087	.000

Table 3 above revealed the relative contribution of the independent variables expressed in beta weights to the dependent variable, the findings revealed that locus of control ($\beta = .260$, $p < .05$) had significant relative contribution to lecturers multimedia technologies utilisation ($\beta = .163$, $p < .05$). This connotes that lecturers' locus of control is a correlate of their multimedia technologies utilisation in Colleges of Education in south-west. Nigeria.

Discussion of findings

The finding revealed that majority of the lecturers in colleges of education in south-west Nigeria, exhibited high level of locus of control although most of them of exhibited more of external locus of control that internals. Applying knowledge acquired through discussion with colleagues and group to improve lecturers' use of multimedia technologies ability for academic productivity, assistance of colleagues at workplace enhance lecturers' multimedia technologies utilization greatly through, multimedia technology skill acquired by getting along with the IT experts around them to enhance their multimedia technologies utilisation.

Also, lecturers' personal interest, skills, professional exposure and multimedia technologies utilisation enhance their teaching effectiveness, taking active part in multimedia technologies aided academic work can control events in teaching and multimedia technology skills are determined by lecturers' personal agitation and hard work. This finding is in line with the findings of Kay-Cheng, (2015) in an investigation on Locus of control as an arbitrator of teachers stress, Although Key-Cheng found that interaction with other teachers sometimes enhanced teachers' effectiveness but person interest in self-development ability improved teachers' effectiveness more than collective or peer influence teachers' effectiveness. Likewise, this finding is in line with Wood, Saylor and Cohen (2009) that people with inner locus of control reinforcement trust that their conducts with their professionals decide and the reinforcement they get. They believe in their ability to influence their immediate personal

effort environment and sociological factors to improve their outcome o their daily life. It could be observed that, there was a high level of locus of control among the respondents.

On the use of multimedia technologies in colleges of education in south-west, Nigeria, the finding revealed that multimedia technologies utilisation is at an average level, it was further revealed that lecturers frequently uses Mobile Phones, social Media, Internet Facilities and Laptop/ i –pad. This finding is in variance with Hoffman (2002) who found a high level of multimedia technologies in elementary school in Scotland, Aleburu (2008) who found an average use of multimedia technologies in early education process for cultural related studies in Ghana. Although they both expressed that multimedia technologies utilisation make teaching/ learning arrangement enjoyable and motivating with changing images, sounds, symbols, its effects could also be helpful in teaching concepts, ideas and reduce boredom on the part of the teacher and learners.

The finding established a relationship between lecturers' locus of control and their multimedia technologies utilisation in colleges of education in southwest, Nigeria. This finding is in line with Chung and Ding (2002) and Kay-Cheng (2015) on the investigation on locus of control and work outcome they revealed a relationship between the two variables.

Conclusion and recommendation

This study investigated locus of control as a correlate of lecturers' use of multimedia technologies in colleges of education in southwest, Nigeria. The variable has the possibility of improving the use of multimedia technologies in colleges of education. It was specifically found out that lecturers' external locus of control was high while their internal locus of control was low. Furthermore lecturers' multimedia technologies utilisation for lectures was technologies were average and lecturers' locus of control has relationship with their multimedia technologies utilisation in colleges of education in south-west, Nigeria.

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Government agencies in charge of tertiary education in Nigeria should monitor and encourage the implementation of the use of multimedia technologies in school curriculum in Nigerian colleges of education to enhance it effective use in knowledge transmission,

2. The government representatives (Governing council) in the colleges of education should ensure the employment of vibrant lecturers who can adapt to the technological change in our society for effective knowledge impartation in their students
3. Lecturers and pre-service teachers should undertake mandatory practical training and retraining on multimedia technologies and its effective utilisation in education. These will provide them with practical and functional knowledge of multimedia, internet and associated technologies for effectiveness and competence.

References

- Akinjide, B. O. (2010). Concern for product and people leadership style: Moderating effect of working environment. *Journal Management* 26.1: 211-220.
- Akintayo, D. I. (2016). Locus of control and job satisfaction as predictors of Perceived non-teaching staffs` productivity in higher institutions in Ogun state, Nigeria. *Global Advanced Research Journal of Management and Business Studies* 1.6 : 181-187. Retrieved on 24th July, 2016 from <http://garj.org/garjmbs/index.htm>
- Aleburu, V.I. (2008). *Using Educational Media for Effective Teaching in E.O Adeniyi., T. Ajobiwe. & A.A Adejumobi, R. O. (2008). A handbook on Effective Classroom practices for Participants In Federal Teachers' Scheme, UBEC, publication, pg 71-94.*
- Chung Y. Y., and Ding, C. G. (2002). Development of the scales locus of control scale. *Journal of Occupational Organisational Psychology* 75.2: 233-245. Retrieved on 23rd June, 2015 from <http://dx.doi.org/10.1348/09631790260098514>.
- Egunjobi A. O. (2012). *Concise and Basic Concepts of Educational Technology*. Ibadan JETSOL Publishers.
- Hoffman. B. (2002). What drives successful technology planning? *Journal of Information Technology for Instructor Education* 5.1/2: 46-59.
- Wood, A. M., Saylor, C. and Cohen, J. (2009). Locus of control and academic success among ethnically diverse baccalaureate nursing students. *Nurs Educ Perspect* 30. 5: 290- 294. Retrieved on 23rd March, 2015 from <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/19824238>.
- Kay-Cheng, S. (2014). Relation between Investment Objective and Demographic Variable. *Journal of General Management Research* 1.1: 91 - 100.

- Lefcourt, H. M. (1982). *Locus of control*. Hillsdale, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
- McCoach, C. O., Gable, M. N. and Madara, O. O. (2013). Factors influencing Research Productivity among Lecturers in Teachers' Colleges in Zimbabwe. *Southern African Journal of Education Science and Technology* 1. 2: 118-124.
- Onasanya, S.A., Shehu, R.A.; Oduwaye, R.O. and Shehu, L.A. (2010). Higher institutions lecturers' attitude towards integration of ICT into teaching and research *Journal of Information technology*. <http://scialert.net/abstract/>.
- Taiwo, S.A. (2008). Principles Underlying The Improvisation of Teaching Aids for Effective Classroom Management in Adeniyi E.O. Ajobiwe, T & Adejumobi A.A. (2008). *A handbook on effective Classroom practices for Participants in Federal Teachers Scheme*, UBEC, publication, 54-70.
- Adeagbo, O. O. (2015). Influence of Locus of Control and Computer Skills on the Use of Internet Resources by Undergraduate Students in Nigerian Universities, *Library Philosophy and Practice*. Retrieved on 28th February, 2016 from <http://unllib.unl.edu/LPP>
- Konan, N. (2013). Educational supervisors' locus of control. *Eurasian Journal of Educational Research* 51: 45-64.
- Shabazz, K. M. (2007). The effects of environment and age on locus of control, self-efficacy, and self-esteem of military and non- military students' academic achievement (Unpublished doctoral dissertation). Tourou University International.
- Chen, J. C., and Silverthorne, C. (2008). Impact of locus of control on job stress, job performance and job satisfaction in Taiwan. *Journal of Leadership Organisational Development* 29.7: 572-582.
- Chhabra, B. (2013). Locus of control as a moderator in the relationship between job Effectiveness and organizational commitment: A study of Indian IT professionals. *Organizations and Markets in Emerging Economies* 4(2/8): 25-41. Retrieved on the 25th May 2018 from http://www.om.ef.vu.lt/cms/cache/RePEc_files/article_47.pdf.
- Carrim, N. M. H., Basson, J., and Coetzee, M. (2006). The relationship between job satisfaction and locus of control in a South African call centre environment. *South African Journal of Labour Relations* 30.2: 66-81.
- Dollinger, S. J. (2000). Locus of Control and Incidental Learning: An application to College Student Success. *College Student Journal* 34. 4: 20-34.
- McCoach, C. O., Gable, M. N. and Madara, O. O. (2013). Factors influencing Research Productivity among Lecturers in Teachers' Colleges in Zimbabwe. *Southern African Journal of Education Science and Technology* 1. 2: 118-124.
- Mc Peek, O. C. (2012). Need for achievement, locus of control and the prediction of business start-ups: A longitudinal study. *Journal of Economic Psychology* 24. 3: 56-68

Ogunmakin, O. O. and Akomolafe, A. O. (2013). Locus of control and academic achievement: A literature review. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology* 44, 419-427.